

THEORETICAL, SOCIO-POLITICAL NATURE OF SPIRITUAL-EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITY.

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Annotation: *Today, due to the intensification of globalization, new threats and dangers to peace and stability in our country, a critical assessment of the work done in our country to unite the society around the national idea, to improve it on the basis of new requirements.*

Keywords: *National idea, globalization, peace, stability, threat, spiritual and enlightenment activity, national values, national unity, ideological immunity.*

The system of propaganda aimed at strengthening the spiritual and enlightenment foundations of society in the Republic of Uzbekistan during the years of independence, the implementation of the basic concepts and principles of national independence, increasing the sense of responsibility for the fate and future of our country, especially in the hearts of our compatriots, especially the younger generation. formed and certain work was done. However, “Today, globalization is intensifying in the world, and new threats and dangers to peace and stability are growing. Such a complex and dangerous situation requires a critical assessment of the work done in the field and the improvement of its activities in line with modern requirements []].

Indeed, in today's world, globalization is intensifying, and new threats and dangers to peace and stability are growing. In particular, the upbringing of young people in families, neighborhoods and educational institutions, the superficial conduct of targeted ideological and educational work with unorganized youth in remote areas and neighborhoods, misguided involvement in crime, extremism and terrorism, disregard for national values, early marriage, family divorce. the fact that advocacy efforts to prevent cases do not yield the expected results in most cases requires serious attention to these issues.

In such a difficult situation, it is necessary to unite the society around the national idea, to mobilize for creative work in accordance with the

requirements of the Action Strategy for the further development of Uzbekistan, to raise awareness of complex ideological processes in the world.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said, “Our spiritual directions should be ten steps ahead of economic ones. Then the great plans and programs that we are currently implementing will be realized. ” These ideas have laid the foundation for strengthening and developing the spiritual heritage of our people as one of the main foundations for the renewal and development of Uzbekistan. The ongoing spiritual and educational work plays an important role in the implementation of the Action Strategy based on the five directions of development of Uzbekistan, the development of national thinking, building a civil society based on the harmony of universal and national values.

The spiritual and enlightenment activities carried out in our country are based primarily on the spiritual and enlightenment heritage of our people. After all, this heritage is a national ideology, a solid source of our spirituality. Therefore, in the context of spiritual and educational tasks, it is important to establish a practical education that instills in our minds the national ideology. National ideology is essentially a social pedagogical, technological mechanism, an integral part of spiritual and educational work - based on ideological education, and involves the main tasks such as persuasion, organization, mobilization, spiritual stimulation, the formation of ideological immunity. After all, the main goal and driving force of social and pedagogical reforms in the country is the creation of conditions and effective mechanisms for the realization of individual interests, the transformation of old thinking and social behavioral skills.

The essence of the activity of a social pedagogue, that is, a social pedagogue is an employee of each center of spirituality and enlightenment - a specialist in socio-educational work with children, parents, adolescents, youth, adults in educational institutions, housing. - It is not difficult to feel the relevance of educational work and the socio-pedagogical competencies of employees in this field.

Spiritual and educational activities, social, integrative pedagogical support of the national idea propaganda are extremely important for our time. At the same time, the spiritual and enlightenment sphere covers such aspects as the restoration of our national educational values, their collection, study, and the delivery of them to the people as the basis of our spiritual policy.

Spiritual education, first of all, envisages the achievement of our national idea in the personal, practical qualities (social skills) of the population and youth. However, some concepts, ideas may be close to the heart, influential, while others may remain only at the level of information, knowledge, and do not become beliefs. Belief arises as a result of the synthesis of generalized facts and data, knowledge. Belief, as the knowledge that has become the inner position of the individual, determines a person's attitude to the world, homeland, nation, self, guides his behavior and activities.

In the Address of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Chambers of the Oliy Majlis and in his subsequent speeches, specific social orders were given to the only science of youth education - pedagogy to cultivate faith and devotion to the Fatherland in young people. Including,

"Well, we need young people who love the nation, the country, even if they have less experience"; "We need patriotic journalists"; "Ambassador must be patriotic"; "Why the national idea? It is necessary to love the motherland ", " Passing the heritage of great artists to the people has a great impact on patriotism "; "We need to raise the quality of education to a new level"; "The fight against spiritual threats needs to be strengthened"; "It should be noted that the level of moral and spiritual training of soldiers and officers lags behind the requirements of today's rapidly changing times."

Under the general guidance of the author, the Republican Center for Spirituality and Enlightenment has developed a "Concept for increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work in the Republic of Uzbekistan" based on the conceptual ideas of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev. The concept is developed on the basis of the main principles and priorities of the spiritual and enlightenment policy pursued in the country. identifies current issues related to education in the spirit of involvement in the ongoing reforms and ways to address them, the role and importance of governmental and non-governmental organizations, family, community, educational institutions in this regard, based on cooperation.

In the Concept of Enhancing the Effectiveness of Spiritual and Enlightenment Work in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the rapidly changing world in the implementation of spiritual and enlightenment work requires a new perspective and thinking. Special attention will be paid to the transformation of the national idea into an ideology of action and its improvement in line with real socio-political changes in the life of Uzbekistan today. Spiritual and enlightenment work has been developed as a priority of

the state policy in our country and serves as a conceptual basis for spiritual and enlightenment work in our country.

Spiritual and educational work - to strengthen the sense of devotion to the Fatherland, regardless of nationality, language and profession, to unite our people around the national idea in a difficult and dangerous period of globalization, to be spiritually awake and vigilant, to feel the responsibility entrusted to us. aimed at mobilizing a selfless struggle against alien ideas. After all, if a person is left out of this activity, he can make ideological mistakes and even commit actions that tarnish the honor of his country, his people, his parents. It states that he has a "extreme view of life, a spiritual and moral contradiction, and a" sectarian "interpretation of Islam." This is due to the shortcomings in the educational institutions, the family, the ideological upbringing in the neighborhood where he studied. These and other similar examples require that spiritual education be conducted on a socio-pedagogical basis, in a consistent and differentiated manner.

The main goal of spiritual and educational work is the implementation of a national strategy aimed at maintaining a stable socio-spiritual environment in the country, building a democratic state governed by the rule of law and a strong civil society. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-3160 of July 28, 2017 "On further enhancing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work" separatism, human trafficking, "mass culture", drug trafficking and other threats to the effective ideological struggle [] ". Within the framework of this task, it is necessary to carry out large-scale work in the following areas:

- formation of a healthy socio-spiritual environment in society:
 - to turn the rich historical, scientific, artistic, cultural-enlightenment and moral heritage of the Uzbek people into the spiritual property of every citizen, to realize the goal of national identity as a priority, to inculcate national ideas and ideology in the minds and hearts of the people. - transformation into a source of power;
 - formation of an active civic position of involvement in various segments of the population, in particular, youth, strengthening the sense of devotion and patriotism, the formation of an independent and conscious attitude to political processes in the world and the country;
 - the formation of the qualities of human relations, respect, kindness, interethnic harmony, interreligious tolerance in society, the establishment of systematic and continuous propaganda in this regard in accordance with the principles of national ideology and spirituality;

- to prevent the negative impact on the minds of our youth of ideas disseminated in various media and the Internet, contrary to our traditions and national mentality, promoting obscenity and immorality;

- Further improvement of educational work, the formation of high moral qualities in young people, universal values, national identity, a sense of pride, a healthy lifestyle, preparation for independent family life based on rich historical and cultural heritage, based on the traditions and customs of our people. to find a place in society, to strengthen the desire to acquire a profession;

- To prevent the negative impact of threats under the guise of "popular culture" on the lives of young people and to develop in them a strong ideological immunity;

- The development of modern heroes by promoting the achievements of young people in various fields and the formation in their minds of the ideal of a harmoniously developed personality.

The system of spiritual and enlightenment work is a continuous technological process, which consists of a set of interrelated socio-political, legal, socio-economic, ideological, educational, cultural and enlightenment activities carried out by governmental and non-governmental organizations under the leadership of the Republican Council of Spirituality and Enlightenment. .

One of the main criteria for the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work is the moral requirements of society to the younger generation, the degree to which it is compatible with the content, form, style and technology of spiritual and educational work.

The expected result of the socio-technological approach to spiritual and enlightenment work is the increase in the effectiveness of spiritual and enlightenment work in society, high moral and ethical qualities of the population, civic position, active implementation of the Action Strategy, love for the Fatherland and its immunity to foreign ideas.

Consistent implementation of spiritual and educational work will increase the morale of the citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan, provide our youth with modern knowledge and high competencies, strong will, active citizenship.

References:

1. From the resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from July 28, 2017 "About increase of efficiency of spiritual and educational work and raising of development of branch to a new level"

2. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis <http://uza.uz/en/documents/president> of the Republic of Uzbekistan

3. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 28, 2017 No PP-3160 "On further increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work."